

ABSTRACT

The proposed theory about cognition in design aims to contribute to the understanding of the operating mode of designers, considering the model of thought behind it that holds characteristics of a particular nature. This knowledge is extrapolated to cases of incomplete problems resolution inherent to reality complexity, consider the model of technical rationality which based the current operating conditions of capitalism. The sustainability of current lifestyles based on consumption is placed on analysis, with design thinking to solve problems where there is a visual literacy along with a verbal literacy. The potential of the visual mode, close to the sensory experience without loss of original meaning, let us point to the possibility of imaterial transactions with symbolic-analytic products. Advocating a dematerialization of consumption it is proposed to develop solutions for sustainability in different contexts of human activity, based on cognitive processes broader and with better achievements.

Keywords: design, cognition, visual thinking, sustainability, capitalism, consumption, dematerialization